

Heterocyclic Compounds : Sulphur as a Potential Oxidant : Preparation of 5-Alkyl/arylimino-2,4-dialkyl/aryl- 3-thio/oxo-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines

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Some interesting observations involving reaction of excess of benzylamine and isoperthiocyanic acid (Ia), the so-called isothiocyanate sulphides (Ib-Ij) and isothiocyanate oxides (II) have been reported. In these reactions 5-alkyl/arylimino-2,4-dialkyl/aryl-3-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines (III) and 5-arylimino-2,4-dialkyl/aryl-3-oxo-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines (VI) have been isolated. In all these reactions, elemental sulphur initially formed acts as a potential oxidant in the oxidative cyclisation of intermediates, viz., 2,4-dithiobiurets (IV) and 2-thiobiurets (VII).

I NTERACTION of 5-imino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidine called isoperthiocyanic acid (Ia) and compounds related to this, i.e., 4-substituted-5-substituted imino-3-thio-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (Ib-Ij) and 3-oxo-4-substituted-5-substituted imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (II) also called isothiocyanate sulphides and oxides, respectively, with aryl and alkyl amines has been investigated earlier¹⁻⁴. We have now noticed that interaction of excess of benzylamine with I and II gives the related 1,2,4-thiadiazolidines, 2,4-dithiobiurets and 2-thiobiurets, depending upon the reaction conditions, viz., boiling benzylamine or boiling ethanol media. All these have been prepared for the first time. The present communication is a record of these investigations.

When the interaction of Ia has been carried out in boiling benzylamine for 3 hr, evolution of hydrogen sulphide is quite perceptible. On treatment with aqueous hydrochloric acid, a product, crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 146° is isolated. The product is found non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. It did not react with phenyl isothiocyanate, nor with carbon disulphide indicating the absence of a free imino group. The ir spectrum of the product clearly showed $\nu_{C=S}$ (1200 cm^{-1}), $\nu_{C=N}$ (1580 cm^{-1}) and ν_{C-S} (705 cm^{-1})^{7,8} bands. A band due to ν_{S-S} , however, is missing. On the basis of all these facts, the product is assigned the structure 5-benzylimino-2,4-dibenzyl-3-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (IIIa).

When the interaction of Ia has been carried out with benzylamine in boiling ethanolic medium,

elemental sulphur is left as residue on cooling and filtering. The alcoholic filtrate on treatment with dilute hydrochloric acid gives a product, crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 140°. This product is found desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On boiling with benzylamine, in presence of elemental sulphur, it is oxidatively cyclized into IIIa with evolution of hydrogen sulphide. Therefore, it is expected to be 1,3,5-tribenzyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (IVa).

Formation of IIIa from the direct reaction of Ia and benzylamine and formation of IVa on reaction of Ia and benzylamine in ethanolic medium and conversion of IVa into IIIa has demonstrated the exact path of the reaction in which elemental sulphur acts as an oxidant for IVa. The mechanism may be stated as follows :

The formation of IIIa will essentially take place through an intermediate 1,2,4-dithiazolidine Va⁸ (not isolated) which is not likely to survive in basic conditions and therefore will be rearranged into IIIa.

When the interaction of benzylamine and Ib has been carried out without any solvent, hydrogen

sulphide is found eliminated and the product, m.p. 145° has been isolated. It is assigned the structure 2-benzyl-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-3-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (IIb) on the basis of the following facts :

The product is found non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. The ir spectrum of the product clearly showed the presence of $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ (1200 cm^{-1}), $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ (1580 cm^{-1}) and $\nu\text{C}-\text{S}$ (705 cm^{-1})^{7,8} bands.

When the reaction of benzylamine is extended to other isothiocyanate sulphides (Ic-Ig), the related products IIIc-IIIg have been isolated.

Ib on reaction with benzylamine in boiling ethanolic medium did not give 5-benzyl-1,3-diaryl-2,4-dithiobiurets. In most of the cases, unreacted product is isolated while in the case of reaction with Ib, small quantity of 3-benzyl-1-phenyl thiocarbamide, m.p. 149° along with elemental sulphur is detected.

The reaction of benzylamine with IIa has also been carried out both in boiling benzylamine medium and boiling ethanolic medium. In the former, hydrogen sulphide is eliminated and a solid, m.p. 134° has been isolated. This has been assigned structure 2-benzyl-3-oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (VIa) on the basis of the following facts :

The product is non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. The ir spectrum of the product clearly indicated the presence of $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ (1620 cm^{-1}), $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ (1580 cm^{-1}) and $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ (705 cm^{-1}) bands.

The reaction of Ia and benzylamine in boiling ethanolic medium forms a product, crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 138° along with elemental sulphur. The product is identified through m.m.p. as 5-benzyl-1,3-diphenyl-2, thiobiuret (VIIa)⁹. VIIa is oxidized to VIa on boiling with benzylamine in presence of elemental sulphur. On reaction with benzylamine, Iib and Iic give VIb and VIc respectively. All these reactions may be represented as follows :

- where (a) R=R'=Hydrogen (in I only) and R=R'=Benzyl
 (b) R=R'=Phenyl
 (c) R=Phenyl, R'=p-Tolyl
 (d) R=Phenyl, R'=m-Tolyl
 (e) R=Phenyl, R'=p-Chlorophenyl
 (f) R=Phenyl, R'=m-Chlorophenyl

where R=R'=(a) Phenyl, (b) p-Tolyl, (c) Methyl (in II only) and benzyl (in VI only)

Experimental

The required isoperthiocyanic acid¹⁰, isothiocyanate sulphides¹¹ and isothiocyanate oxides¹² were prepared according to procedures described earlier.

(1) Interaction of isoperthiocyanic acid (Ia) and benzylamine :

(a) *Reaction without solvent* : When to isoperthiocyanic acid (2 g) is added benzylamine (10 ml), it gradually dissolves with liberation of heat. It is then refluxed for 3 hr when hydrogen sulphide is evolved. The reaction mixture is cooled to 0° and slowly acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid (4 N) without allowing the temperature to rise above 10°. A sticky solid is obtained which is triturated several times with petroleum ether when a white solid (IIIa) is obtained. It is crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 146° (Found : N, 10.45 ; S, 15.05. C₂₈H₂₁N₃S₂ requires N, 10.42 ; S, 15.99%).

(b) *Reaction in ethanolic medium* : Isoperthiocyanic acid (2 g) is suspended in 20 ml ethanol and 10 ml benzylamine is added. It is then refluxed for 1 hr. The evolution of hydrogen sulphide and ammonia are clearly perceptible. After 1 hr the reaction mixture is cooled. The elemental sulphur that separates out is filtered off, and the filtrate is acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid (4 N) with cooling when a white sticky mass, solidified on trituration with petroleum ether followed by ethanol, is obtained. It is crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 140° (Found : N, 9.88 ; S, 15.93. C₂₈H₂₃N₃S₂ requires N, 10.37 ; S, 15.81%).

(2) Interaction of isothiocyanate sulphides (Ib-Ig) and benzylamine :

Details of a typical experiment (where R=R'=phenyl) are as follows :

To 2 g of isothiocyanate sulphide is added 10 ml of benzylamine. The solution warmed up as soon as benzylamine is added. It is then refluxed for 3 hr when evolution of hydrogen sulphide is noticed. After 3 hr, the reaction mixture is worked up as usual when a solid, crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 145° is obtained (Found : N, 11.80 ; S, 17.20. C₂₁H₁₇N₃S₂ requires N, 11.20 ; S, 17.07%).

TABLE 1—4-ARYL-2-BENZYL-5-PHENYLIMINO-3-THIO-1,2,4-THIAZOLIDINE(III) AND 4-ARYL-5-ARYLIMINO-2-BENZYL-3-OXO-1,2,4-THIAZOLIDINE(VI)

Reactants for III : I, 2 g and benzylamine 10 ml.
Reactants for VI : II, 2 g and benzylamine 10 ml.

Sl. No.	1,2,4-dithiazolidine	1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (g) m.p. °C	Analysis	
			Found	Required
1.	4-Phenyl-5-phenylimino-3-thio-(Ib)	2-Benzyl-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-3-thio-(IIIb)(2) 145°	N, 11.86 S, 17.20	11.20 17.07
2.	5-Phenylimino-4-p-tolyl-3-thio-(Ic)	2-Benzyl-5-phenylimino-4-p-tolyl-3-thio-(IIIc)(1.8) 146°	N, 10.47 S, 15.96	10.80 16.45
3.	5-Phenylimino-4-m-tolyl-3-thio-(Id)	2-Benzyl-5-phenylimino-4-m-tolyl-3-thio-(IIId)(1.5) 143°	N, 11.14 S, 16.03	10.80 16.45
4.	4-p-Chlorophenyl-5-phenylimino-3-thio-(Ie)	2-Benzyl-4-p-chlorophenyl-5-phenylimino-3-thio-(IIIe)(2) 147°	N, 10.44 S, 15.89	10.26 15.62
5.	4-m-Chlorophenyl-5-phenylimino-3-thio-(If)	2-Benzyl-4-m-chlorophenyl-5-phenylimino-3-thio-(IIIIf)(1.8) 142°	N, 9.98 S, 15.77	10.26 15.62
6.	3-Oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-(IIa)	2-Benzyl-3-oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-(VIA)(2) 134°	N, 11.29 S, 9.41	11.69 8.91
7.	3-Oxo-4-p-tolyl-5-p-tolylimino-(IIb)	2-Benzyl-3-oxo-4-p-tolyl-5-p-tolylimino-(VIb)(2) 125°	N, 10.57 S, 7.88	10.85 8.26
8.	4-Methyl-5-methylimino-3-oxo-(IIc)	5-Benzylimino-2,4-dibenzyl-3-oxo-(VIC)(1.6) 136°	N, 11.88 S, 9.19	11.69 8.91

The reaction of benzylamine has been extended to other 4-aryl-5-phenylimino-3-thio-1, 2, 4-dithiazolidines (Ib-If), and the corresponding 1,2,4-thiadiazolidines (IIIb-IIIIf) have been isolated in excellent yields. These are listed in Table 1.

(3) *Interaction of isothiocyanate oxides (IIa-IIc) and benzylamine*: Details of a typical experiment (where, R=R'=phenyl) are as follows:

(a) *Reaction without solvent*: To IIa (2 g) is added 10 ml of benzylamine. It is then refluxed for 3 hr when hydrogen sulphide is found eliminated. After 3 hr, the reaction mixture is worked up as usual when a white solid, crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 134° (VIa) is obtained. (Found: N, 11.29; S, 9.41. C₂₁H₁₇N₃SO requires N, 11.69; S, 8.91%).

The reaction of benzylamine when extended to IIb and IIc, the corresponding products VIb and VIc have been obtained. These have been listed in Table 1.

(b) *Reaction in ethanolic medium*: 2 g of isothiocyanate oxide is suspended in 20 ml of ethanol and 1 ml of benzylamine is added. It is refluxed for 3 hr when no hydrogen sulphide is noticed from the reaction. After 3 hr the elemental sulphur that separated out is filtered and the filtrate acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid (4 N) when a white solid, crystallized from ethanol, m. p. 138° (VIIa) is obtained. (Found: N, 10.62; S, 15.88. C₂₁H₁₇N₃SO requires N, 10.71; S, 16.34%).

On refluxing with elemental sulphur and benzylamine for 2 hr VIIa is oxidatively cyclised into VIa with evolution of hydrogen sulphide.

The reaction of benzylamine is also extended to IIb and IIc and the corresponding compounds VIIb and VIIc (where R=R'=benzyl) have been isolated. The formation of latter will occur by the replacement of methyl groups in IIc with a bulky benzyl group.

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